

Table 1. Rice with resistance to blast and brown spot diseases, Mandya, India.

Pedigree	
TR20/Co 29	IET 8159
Ratna Mutant	Acham/IR20
IET6080	Ar 10-169 Mutant
Hema/CR57/Vikram/Shakti/ORSTR952	CR151-79/CR1014
CR151/CR1014	Tellahamsa/W12708
IET6288	WGL 16085/Kakatiya
IET6314	Imp. Sona/Pak. Basmati
Cul-240/IR20	IET6314/Co 2
Lalnakanda/IR30	IR32/Swarnadhan
IR8/Co 25	OS4/Palguna
Dorpany mutant	IR8/IET4141
IET7810	IET4699/Ras 370
IR2061-465-1-5-IR36	IET4699/Bas 370
Hamsraj/Saket 4	IET7748

Audiovisual rice production modules

A 61-module series of audiovisual lessons in rice production may be purchased from IRRI. The modules cover seven topic areas: production management; growth and morphology of rice; production problems and techniques; weeds, diseases, and their control; pests and their control; research design and analysis; and soil relationships. For further information write: IRRI, Communication and Publications Dept., Division R, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Table 2. Reaction of rice varieties to blast symptoms and brown spot disease at Mandya, India.

Scale ^a	Entries (no.)		
	Leaf blast	Neck blast	Brown spot
0-3	78	83	223
4-6	213	217	99
7-9	43	34	12

^aScale: 0-3 = resistant, 4-6 = moderately susceptible, 7-9 = susceptible.

IR36, a promising variety for bacterial blight-prone areas of Haryana

S. A. Malik, H. A. U. Regional Research Station, Uchani, Karnal; S. C. Ahuja, H. A. U. Rice Research Station, Kaul, Kurukshetra; and C. V. S. Malik, H. A. U. Directorate of Research, Hissar, India

IR36 is a semidwarf, medium-maturity rice variety with slender grains and bacterial blight (BB) resistance. In 1981, it was recommended by the central variety release committee for commercial cultivation in India. Varietal trials under BB stress were conducted in 1980-82 kharif at Kaul and Karnal stations.

Performance of IR36 under bacterial blight stress in Haryana, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha) during kharif				Duration (days)	Panicles/m ²	Length-breadth ratio	BB reaction ^a
	1980 (Kaul)	1981 (Karnal)	1982 (Karnal)	Mean				
IR36	5.6	7.0	5.2	5.9	135	269	2.95	3
Jaya	4.4	7.4	6.2	6.0	148	251	2.32	9
PR106	4.3	6.3	5.1	5.2	149	213	2.60	9
Palman 579	4.5	6.8	5.5	5.6	130	243	2.90	5
CD	0.85	0.56	0.89					
CV(%)	11.12	4.0	11.0					

^aBy 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

IR36 yielded better than PR106 and Palman 579 checks and was equal to Jaya (see table). IR36 had more panicles per square meter, and higher length-breadth ratio than all three checks. It matured

earlier than Jaya, which would allow good performance in wheat - rice rotation. BB infestation in 1981 and 1982 kharif was not as high as in 1980 kharif. □

Reaction of released and prerelease rice varieties to various diseases in Karnataka, India

K. T. Pandurang Gowda, S. Kumaraswamy, and R. C. Yaraguntaiah, Plant Pathology Department, Regional Research Station, V. C. Farm, Mandya, India

Blast (B1), brown spot (BS), grain discoloration (GD), and udbatta (UDb) diseases are becoming important in

Reaction of released and prerelease rice varieties to various diseases in Karnataka, India, 1982 kharif.

Variety	Disease score ^a				
	B1		BS	GD	UDb
	Leaf	Neck			
KMS8	R	R	R	R	S
IET6265	R	M	R	M	R
KMS9	R	R	R	R	R
KMS4	R	R	M	R	R
RP850	R	M	R	R	R
KMS7	R	R	R	R	R
KMP66	R	M	M	R	M

CONTINUED ON NEXT PAGE

Karnataka because of their wide distribution during kharif.

Each test variety was surrounded by highly susceptible varieties HR-12 for BL, Binnibhog for BS, and PTB20 for UDb to expose them to natural infection. Observations were recorded using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice. BL and BS were rated by lesion type and percent leaf area affected. Blast incidence after flowering was recorded as percent neck infection, and number of discolored grains per panicle was recorded for GD assessment. Percent infected panicles was recorded for UDb.

KMS7, KMS9, KMS5914, KMP10, KMP39, KMP41, and Jaya had resistant reactions to the four diseases (see table). □

TABLE CONTINUED

Variety	Disease score ^a				
	BL		BS	GD	UDb
	Leaf	Neck			
29509	R	M	M	M	S
KMP101	R	R	M	R	R
Pusa 150	R	R	R	R	M
KMP10	R	R	R	R	R
29781	M	M	R	R	M
HP-1-1	R	R	R	M	M
KMP41	R	R	R	R	R
KMS5914	R	R	R	R	R
KMP39	R	R	R	R	R
ES-18	M	M	M	R	S
Jaya	R	R	R	R	R
IR20	R	R	M	R	R
Rasi	R	M	M	R	M
Mangala	R	R	M	R	M
IR32	M	R	M	R	R

^aR = resistant (0-3 of the 1980 SES scale), M = moderately susceptible (4-6) and, S = susceptible (7-9).

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Evaluation of promising gall midge-resistant cultivars

P. Samal and B. C. Misra, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

Rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood Mason) Mani is a major pest of rice in kharif in many Indian rice growing states. Thirty-eight promising gall midge resistant cultivars developed by breeders were received through the All-India Coordina-

ted Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad, during 1979 kharif for testing at the Central Rice Research Institute, Orissa. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with two replications. Seedlings were spaced at 20 × 15 cm and the plot was fertilized with 60 kg N, 22 kg P, and 25 kg K/ha. Silvershoots were counted at 30 and 50 days after transplanting and average incidence was calculated.

The maximum 32.6% silvershoots was recorded for WGL 26888

(IR22/W12708). Eight cultivars had less than 3% silvershoots, which was significant at the 1% level. They were OR140-9-3 (CR94/RPW6-13), OR158-7-1 (GMR15 18/Pankaj), WGL 26450, WGL 26528, WGL 26536, WGL 26591, WGL 26965, and WGL 27015 (Surekha/Kakatiya). Of these, OR140-9-3, OR158-7-1, and WGL 26450 also had less than 2% silvershoots at Raipur, Rudrur, Bhubaneswar, Mangalore, and Warangal. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought tolerance

Screening wetland rice varieties for drought tolerance

N. K. Mitra, S. Mallik, and S. Biswas, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah 712 102, India

Drought tolerance at vegetative stage is desirable for deepwater rice. Forty varieties (10 recommended, 11 traditional, and 16 improved) including 2 drought-resistant and 1 susceptible check were

Comparative performance^a of some wetland rice varieties under drought stress.

Entry	Initial stand establishment, 21 DS	Drought tolerance, 45 DS	Recovery, 81 DS	Height (cm), 133 DS	Phenotypic acceptability 133 DS
<i>Recommended varieties</i>					
Pankaj	8.3	9	7.6	31.1	8.3
Mahsuri	7.3	9	8.3	49.3	8.3
Swarna (IET 5656)	9	9	9	22.6	8.3
CR 1009	7.6	9	7.6	49.2	7.6
CR1014	7	9	7.6	61.1	7.6
BIET 821	3.6	3.6	5	88	5
<i>Traditional indica</i>					
OC1393	6.3	7.6	6.3	71.3	7
NC487/77	1.6	1	1.6	93.6	1

CONTINUED ON OPPOSITE PAGE